

CONTEMPORARY VS TRADITIONAL VS SOLAR BUILDINGS

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Abstract – The aim of this research is to investigate the history of traditional and contemporary architecture in order to further improve design methodology in passive solar architecture, and presenting an example of an ideal energy efficient house that takes into account climate, comfort, passive solar systems and the history of architecture of Cyprus. Thermal performance of traditional, contemporary and solar buildings is discussed in relation to climate and in terms of the various aspects necessary for understanding such performances. These aspects include architectural design, constructional materials and methods, occupancy patterns and planning. Non-thermal comfort problems arising from the use of both traditional and contemporary buildings are also discussed, together with the attitudes that made the abandonment of traditional buildings and guided the development of contemporary buildings. Finally, recommendations of how traditional buildings can be used appropriately and contemporary buildings improved are considered and discussed. Different architectural and constructional elements and techniques (orientation, natural ventilation, vegetation, insulation, openings, direct gain, shape, thermal insulation, thermal storage, glazing, solar control, exploitation of spaces- solarium, courtyards, roofs, floors) that were used in traditional houses are studied in relation to their use in passive design today and serve as fine examples of energy-saving architecture. Cypriot traditional houses have proved to be superiorly energy-efficient when compared to contemporary homes due to the thermal performance of both cases based on their architectural design. Comparative annual energy use was performed using computer simulation software Energy 10 resulting that the most energy efficient is the experimental solar house (121 kWh/m²) following the traditional (243 kWh/m²) and final the contemporary (368 kWh/m²). Through 2 years hourly monitoring the solar house, using computer data loggers, the internal temperature and relative humidity throughout the year remained steady (within the thermal comfort limits), despite the instability of external temperatures and humidity percentages. Taking into account the general characteristics of the dry climate and the requirements it imposes on the building characteristics and the general characteristics and thermal performance of traditional and contemporary buildings, it may be concluded that traditional buildings in Cyprus meet the requirements imposed by the climate and that these buildings are good enough thermally to perform well under the prevailing weather conditions. Because of Cyprus climate, passive solar architecture works to its full capacity. This means that, a passive solar house has 100% energy saving potential. This theory has not remained at its conceptual stage as the experimental solar house has demonstrated it in practice.

1. INTRODUCTION

It seems as though Cypriot people today often forget how to design with the immediate environment and tend to ignore the climate, while Cyprus society remains preoccupied with forms that are currently fashionable and items manufactured and unsuitably made elsewhere. These “contemporary buildings”, producing and enclosing internal spaces, have been the main interest and an exciting subject for most designers. They have been designed mainly to keep natural phenomena outside, to separate and control conditions from within, as much as possible and at whatever price, relying on mechanical devices and energy consuming systems to do much of the work.

Much contemporary architectural design, however, has lost most of this intimate knowledge. Orientation, design and construction now depend on the economic use of the site or construction. Buildings are considered in terms of cost and profit. Traditional knowledge of planning has been replaced by space standards and guidelines, while constructional techniques were eroded by standard components. The harmony between the building, the site and the communities’ lifestyles has been lost.

Approximately since 9000 BC, until the mid 20th century AD, construction methods have varied only slightly¹. The construction of buildings was economical by using materials found in the area like stone, wood, reeds, earth and terracotta. Structural solutions were simple and effective. For example, the available length of these trees that were to be used as roof rafters established the dimensions of room widths.

In most of the Cypriot architecture there is much wisdom in the method of construction and for the most part, the solutions found and utilised are both ingenious and economic. The buildings are designed and constructed to fully exploit advantages offered by the local climatic conditions and are characterised by:

- The positions in orientation to the sun path either to avoid direct sunlight entering the building of the opposite.
- The exploitation of breezes for ventilation and cross ventilation in the room
- The awareness and exploitation of the nature of flora and its use for practical functions (e.g. medicinal plants)

- A good insulation of walls (40-50cm width) and roofs,
- The small openings on the external walls for maximum insulation.

In order to arrive to some reasonable recommendations for the use of traditional buildings and the improvement of contemporary buildings, it is necessary to consider how such buildings perform under the local climatic conditions and how they cope with other requirements. Such recommendations may then be defined in terms of the advantages of these buildings.

The various aspects necessary for an understanding of the thermal performance of both traditional and contemporary buildings are briefly discussed below. These aspects include architectural design, constructional materials and methods, occupancy patterns and planning. The thermal performance of both traditional and contemporary buildings is evaluated in terms of these aspects and in relation to the local climatic conditions.

2. TRADITIONAL BUILDINGS

These buildings have a square or rectangular plan and a courtyard. They normally consist of two floors built of a composite mud and timber or stone and timber construction. The ground floor is of massive construction with a thickness from 0.6 to 1,2m, the first floor being of a relatively lighter construction and having more external windows. The plan is flexible to permit occupancy patterns, which suit diurnal and seasonal climatic variations.

The thermal performance of traditional buildings is discussed below in relation to the climate, and in terms of the main aspects necessary for and understanding of such performance:

- **Architectural design of traditional buildings**

Traditional buildings are generally south oriented with its long axis along the East-West direction. Then the division of this room called 'Dhichoron' (double space), the addition of other rooms called 'Sospiton' (inner room) and a covered veranda called 'Iliakos' (solarium) were placed.

1. Makrinari
2. Dhichoron
3. Inner room
4. Inner room
5. Iliakos
6. Traditional earth oven.
7. Courtyard.

Due to its orientation and the mild weather conditions of the plain, the 'iliakos' was used as a sitting room, cooking place and generally as a working place. The Solarium is an indispensable solar feature of the Cypriot house and a unique building element in Greek architecture. It was an early instinctive approach to passive solar design. Its solar role was predominant whether acting as an arched corridor, as a central axis or even when it evolved into a self-contained space.

The courtyard is an arrangement that evolved naturally from the climatic conditions, the needs of the family and the social structure of the community. It generally creates a microclimate that moderates the climate surrounding the building. Planted mostly with deciduous vegetation like grapevines, fig trees etc, it offers shade in the summer and admits sun in the winter. It also creates windy sides that are most valuable when one seeks the breeze in the summer and calm corners in the winter. Arched arcades at the perimeter are indispensable to shield the overhead midday sunⁱⁱ.

The inward looking design of traditional buildings is a successful feature from the point of view of thermal performance. The open courtyard works in many ways as a thermal regulator. Its high walls exclude the sun and shade a large area of the inner building surfaces. The fruit trees and grass normally found in the courtyard, contribute to keeping the air cool and providing shade accompanied by visual and psychological relief. Rooms and terraces surrounding the courtyard are normally incorporated in units, each consisting of two or three rooms and a central terrace. The terrace has a roof higher in level than the roof of the surrounding rooms and is usually provided with clerestory windows. The surrounding rooms open towards the terrace and they too may be provided with clerestory windows.

Figure 6.23 "Iliakos" (solarium)

The main unit, which includes the large terrace, is normally placed on the south side of the courtyard. Accordingly, direct sunshine is avoided in summer while in winter the occupants may enjoy the sunshine falling on the exposed north side of the courtyard.

External windows may be found on one or two sides of the building, depending on its position in the planning area. Such windows are limited in number, small in size and positioned high in the wall to reduce the amount of heat admitted into the building and to reduce ground glare in summer. As the width of each window is almost equal to the thickness of the wall, such windows also function as vertical louvers and prevent most of the direct solar radiation from penetrating into buildings.

All the openings were placed to the south wall to provide natural light and heat. Small openings called 'arseres' were also used in every house (Figure 1). These were placed at the upper part of the walls. In summer, they allowed lighter hot air to go out of the house and be replaced by cooler air from outside, while in winter, thymes (small dense bushes) were closing these openings and they provided thermal insulation

Figure 1 "arseres"

- **Constructional materials and methods of traditional building**

For building in Mediterranean countries it is normal to consider the best constructional materials are those, which do not conduct heat. Materials used for the construction of traditional buildings in Cyprus are stone, sun-dried mud-brick and timber. These materials are amongst the poorest conductors of heat. They are also used to erect the massive ground floor construction, which is effective in smoothing the large diurnal temperature variations occurring in summer. Such construction has a high thermal capacity and therefore it absorbs much of the falling solar heat during the day, thereby extending the time before the temperature of the internal surface shows any appreciable increase. The increase in the time lag also makes heat emission into the building take place at a

time when the outdoor shade air temperature is low and the time is then suitable to remove the emitted heat by ventilation. At this time the direction of heat transfer may also be reversed and some of the stored heat may be emitted outwards.

In winter, the massive construction of traditional buildings may also be heated by solar radiation, which dominates for a long time during the day. Heat emitted inwards during the night may then be considered as one of the desirable properties of the structure.

The only rendering material is mud plaster. This material deteriorates quickly despite sometimes being mixed with long pieces of hay to improve its structural and thermal properties. The rendering is therefore usually renewed every year and is usually painted with whitewash both to reflect the solar radiation falling on the high, narrow windows.

- **Occupancy patterns of traditional buildings**

Traditional residential buildings consist of two floors. The occupancy patterns of these buildings vary with the change in both the daily and seasonal weather conditions. The daily changes in occupancy patterns are mostly limited to the summer time, where during the hot hours of the day people seeking protection from the heat, retreat to the ground floor away from the hot regions near the roof. In the evening they expand their activities outdoor and make the courtyard their living space. During the night they move upstairs and use the rooms of the first floor and/or the flat roof for sitting and sleeping.

In winter, the ground floor is rarely used unless it includes the kitchen and other services. The first floor is usually the only space used during the day and night because it is of a relatively lighter construction, easy to heat by solar radiation caught through the windows, which are greater in number and larger in size than those available on the ground floor.

Although the daily movements of the occupants in summer are planned to correspond well with the thermal periods during the 24-hour cycle, an unfortunate habit of the occupants is closing the windows during summer nights when the outdoor temperature falls too low for comfort. The benefits of the overnight ventilation, which if carried out could keep indoor conditions cool during the day, are therefore lost.

In winter however, as the night temperatures are too low and the day temperatures are moderate, the windows are usually kept closed unless opened for ventilation.

- **Planning of traditional buildings**

In addition to the above-considered aspects, which all contribute to the successful thermal performance of traditional buildings; the whole character of traditional architecture is influenced by the climate. The compact way of building with its narrow organic network and courtyard produced large masses of buildings. The rate of heat exchange in the whole building is therefore reduced. Such a compact design made it possible for most walls and a large area of the roof to be shaded during the day. Overhangs and balconies incorporated in the design of traditional buildings all work as shading devices.

Taking into account the general characteristics of the dry climate and the requirements it imposes on the building characteristics and the general characteristics and thermal performance of traditional buildings discussed above, it may be concluded that traditional buildings in Cyprus meet the requirements imposed by the climate and that these buildings are good enough thermally to perform well under the prevailing weather conditions. It should also be mentioned that one of the main factors, which make the thermal performance to these buildings successful, is the integral interaction between their design and the occupancy patterns.

3. CONTEMPORARY BUILDINGS

The architectural design of contemporary buildings (post 1970) in Cyprus is mostly based on the educational experience of local architects. As most Cypriot architects were educated in Europe and the United States, their designs are profoundly influenced by western architecture and there exists a tendency to recreate an international architectural style without considering the advantages of traditional architecture and the distinctive climatic conditions and social life. Furthermore, despite the fact that there are some fine examples of contemporary buildings based on correct design principles and a better understanding of the local climatic conditions, the great majority of contemporary buildings are erected without consideration of the climatic conditions and their influence on comfort and the well being of the occupants. This is mainly due to lack of knowledge about the thermal performance of contemporary constructional materials and methods, and consequently the shortage of building regulations which govern this aspect of the art of building.

However, most contemporary buildings in Cyprus have appropriately designed functional plans. These buildings are also frame-built, flat-roofed and enclosed with thin non-load bearing largely glazed block work walls. Their plans may sometimes be flexible but not so much as to permit occupancy patterns similar to those available in traditional buildings.

The thermal performance of contemporary buildings is discussed below in relation to the climate and in terms of the main aspects necessary for an understanding of such performance. These aspects are as mentioned earlier architectural design, constructional materials and methods, occupancy patterns and planning.

- **Architectural design of contemporary buildings**

The extensive use of reinforced concrete frame in the erection of contemporary buildings has made it possible for structural and non-structural building elements to be well defined. Accordingly, the external walls have almost become non-structural elements dominated by vast glazed windows. The curtain wall, which is a non-supporting skin made up from window mullions and in-fill panels and cantilevered from the frame structure, has also become easier to construct.

The above-mentioned innovations and advancement in building design and technology have made any form of building possible to create with materials such as glass, metal and building panels of every kind characterising the new architecture. These features of contemporary buildings have also created many problems in the Mediterranean countries by being unsuited to the climatic conditions.

Despite the design flexibility possible in the frame-built, non-load bearing wall buildings, the plan development has been neither parallel to the advance in the new technology nor based on the traditional plan form.

- **Constructional materials and constructional methods of contemporary buildings**

Materials used for the construction of contemporary buildings in Cyprus are reinforced concrete, hollow clay bricks for the building structure, glass, wood, steel and aluminium profiles for doors and windows, smooth or granulated ordinary Portland cement plaster and paints for wall finishes, in site concrete, ceramic tiles and linoleum for floor finishes and asphalt, mastic asphalt and bitumen felt for a damp proof course and waterproofing for roofs.

The above-mentioned materials are normally incorporated in semi-heavy-weight constructions inappropriately designed. The roof and external walls are seldom provided with sufficient thermal insulation. They are also not thick enough to compensate for such loss of insulation by having high thermal capacity.

The roof is mostly erected with a thin layer of reinforced concrete of about 12 cm and topped with two layers of hessian damped with mastic asphalt. The upper layer may also be covered with white sand. A layer of screed topped with an emulsion of ordinary

Portland cement or ceramic tiles may also sometimes be added to make the roof usable for sitting and sleeping. Some roofs may also be erected from reinforced concrete ribs and hollow concrete block. The ceiling is mostly covered with plaster and paint.

External walls are mostly erected from a layer of concrete block or hollow clay bricks lined with ordinary Portland cement plaster and painted. The external surface of the concrete block walls is normally rendered and painted. In the rare cases where thermal insulation is applied, expanded polystyrene is usually placed on the inner side of the structure or in cavity walls. All other internal surfaces are normally plastered and painted.

- **Occupancy patterns of contemporary buildings**
Residential buildings are usually occupied continuously or intermittently. It is however normal to find more than 90% of the occupants at home by 3.00 p.m. in summer. As the structure of contemporary buildings is with a short time-lag of the order of 2 to 3 hours and as the maximum amount of solar radiation falling on buildings in summer takes place at midday and the maximum outdoor shade air temperature appears at about 2.00 p.m., the maximum temperature of the external surface appears at about 1.00 p.m. Accordingly, the maximum temperature of the internal surface appears about 3.00 or 4.00 p.m. Heat emission into buildings therefore takes place during the resting time of the occupants, when the outdoor shade air temperature is still high and such heat cannot be removed by ventilation. Moveable fans are widely used. But with little effect on improving the indoor conditions because the draught of external air is already of a high temperature and the distribution of air movement is non-homogenous. The overall result is physiological and psychological dissatisfactionⁱⁱⁱ.

As many contemporary residential buildings are comprised of apartments normally designed with a specific function for each space, the occupants are obliged to carry out their activities in the specified zones regardless of the daily and seasonal change in weather conditions. Alternative spaces, which can be used to avoid the overheating effects at certain times of the day, seldom exist.

Despite the fact that an appropriate control strategy of the windows may significantly help in controlling the indoor environment, such control is not applied for several reasons. Amongst these reasons is the lack of awareness of the importance of such control, mainly due to lack of advice. Other reasons are providing ventilation during the day and avoiding noise generated by heavy traffic during the night.

In the winter, windows are normally kept closed unless they are open for ventilation at certain times of the day and night.

3. TRADITIONAL VS CONTEMPORARY

The different aspects of both traditional and contemporary buildings, discussed above, are summarised and given in table 1. The similar aspects of these buildings may therefore be compared with each other and an appreciation of the thermal performance of both traditional and contemporary buildings in relation to the climate shall be clarified.

From the thermal performance point of view, traditional buildings are much better than inappropriately designed contemporary buildings. This means that thermal performance is not the only criterion by which the use or abandonment of traditional and contemporary buildings may be evaluated.

The present advance in design and technology, which may have been misused because of lack of knowledge and experience and has as a result created inappropriately designed contemporary buildings, has also stimulated awareness of many short-comings in the design of traditional buildings which do not match the requirements of contemporary urban life. Advances in design and technology have also provided many means by which the shortcomings of contemporary buildings may be overcome, and much improved new buildings incorporating the design advantages of both traditional and contemporary buildings may be created-such as creation of the experimental solar house.

- **Problems related to hygiene considerations**
One of the main reasons why contemporary buildings are preferred to the traditional is that they provide all the necessary hygiene services, lighting and ventilation. Most traditional buildings lack sufficient lighting and ventilation and suffer from shortages in services.

- **Problems related to weathering**
Weathering problems of contemporary buildings are closely related to the two main aspects of the climate of Cyprus, mentioned above, i.e. the high values of solar radiation during summer and the subsequent wide diurnal and annual range of outdoor shade air temperature. The influence of the two above-mentioned aspects on contemporary buildings is much greater than that on traditional buildings mainly because traditional building materials belong to the local environment, while those of contemporary buildings are mostly imported or have poor qualities. Weathering problems of traditional buildings are almost limited to the mud

rendering of the external surfaces and the exposed internal surfaces. Such problems are also caused by rainfall, which make such rendering weak, soluble, and in need of almost annual replacement.

The necessity of annual maintenance does, however, make traditional materials unsuitable for use in the new urban towns and cities. It is therefore inevitable that contemporary materials be used, which means that weathering problems affecting these materials should be pointed out and avoided. The high surface temperature of the building structure during summer days increases the rate of deterioration of the low night air temperature, making many materials brittle and subject to cracking under stress. High solar radiation values have great effects on organic building materials. As these materials are mainly composed of long-chain molecules held together by secondary forces, the energy required to break the primary bonds and dislocate the individual molecules is of the same order as that of the ultraviolet radiation. Such materials are therefore liable to degradation because of solar radiation received during summer days. Deterioration of building cladding materials caused by solar radiation means that such deterioration is in turn transferred to the fabric. To prevent such deterioration from taking place, adequate thermal insulation and movement joints are required.

	-Shortages in services	-Zoning problems
Thermal performance	-Satisfactory during both summer and winter and at all times.	-Unsatisfactory during the times of overheating and under heating.
Non-thermal comfort problems	-Necessity of annual maintenance -Shortages in services -Shortages in natural lighting and ventilation -Inaccessibility in case of emergency	-Weathering problems -No adequate building regulations -High influence of the building contractors -Acoustic problems
Demand	-Decreasing because of being not suitable for contemporary urban life	-Increasing because of social and economic changes and contemporary life

4. EXPERIMENTAL SOLAR HOUSE

In this research, a detached house was used because this represents the worst arrangement from the point of view of a thermal environment. A detached house has greater heat losses in the winter and heat gains in summer than terrace houses or blocks of flats, because all the external envelope of a detached house is exposed to the external conditions.

Thermal mass may not be restricted in the exterior walls. Exterior walls may be insulated and lightweight and interior separating walls can be made with blocks or with concrete, which has a high thermal effusivity. The thermal mass can be located on the floor or on the roof. A thickness of 10cm of a massive material (concrete or brick) is quite suitable for providing coolness for the span of one day or for storing passive heat during a winter day.

Another consideration, apart from the U-values, is the skill capacity of the local workmen. The building technique must be easily comprehensible and executable; otherwise care must be taken to find extraordinary workmen.

In order to progress to the ultimate level the theory of the Cypriot solar house, the process of construction was commenced. The principle of design and construction of the solar house is based on the theories and findings on passive solar architecture in Cyprus^{iv}, in and inevitable compromise with local building codes and town planning regulations.

The construction was decided to be a concrete frame and floors and roof (constructed as the typical Cypriot contemporary home, 250mm brick work + 70mm expanded polystyrene and plaster on the interior and exterior of the walls^v. 70mm expanded polystyrene was used to cover the whole building, including walls

ASPECT	TRADITIONAL BUILDINGS	CONTEMPORARY BUILDINGS
Architectural Design	-Inward looking with courtyard -Square or rectangular plan -One or two floors -Covered terraces -A body of water and fountain -Clerestory windows -Flat, domed and vaulted roofs	-Outward looking -Free plan form -Multi-storey blocks -Small balconies -Vast glazed windows -Flat or pitched roofs
Constructional materials and methods	-Local materials found on the site of the building or brought from a nearby area -Simple constructions -Load-bearing walls	-Materials are mostly imported or locally made with poor qualities -Frame structures -Simple constructions -No insulation -Non-load bearing walls
Occupancy patterns	-Changed in residential buildings. The ground floor is used in summer days and the first floor in summer nights and in winter	-Unchanged in residential buildings because of the design restrictions of contemporary buildings
Planning	-Compact planning with courtyard	-Incompact planning. No courtyard

concrete beams, columns and roof. In this way thermal bridges are excluded.

Winter indoor temperatures have also been successful^{vi}. Enough solar heat storage was collected and stored during daytime and released with the appropriate rate in order to maintain pleasant nightly temperature. The fireplace was used to top up the heat on occasions when winter evening temperatures dropped below the norms. In the winter of 2000 these were only 8 times and the winter of 2001 these were 10 times. The fireplace was lit on average three to four hours per night and the warmth was retained until well into the next morning.

5. TRADITIONAL VS CONTEMPORARY VS SOLAR

ENERGY-10 is software used for a specific project and is designed to develop guidelines for low-energy buildings. The author for the initial design concept of the Experimental Solar House has used it.

In order to place a contemporary house into perspective, one must exhibit the comparison between the energy performances of a contemporary house, one that was built post 1970, as it relates to its counterpart, a house built with older building techniques, in the traditional way. The most important difference in the construction specifications of these house, as they are portrayed here is in the construction of the traditional house's wall (adobe versus concrete and bricks) and in the roof (earth versus concrete). The traditional house follows the characteristics discussed previously. It transpires from the results produced, that the energy performance of the organically insulated traditional house is clearly superior that of the contemporary house with no energy-efficient considerations.

As was expected, upon comparing quantitatively the Experimental Solar House with the contemporary house, the solar house proves to be far superior in its energy savings performance. For instance, the contemporary house requires an astounding 4.95 Cyprus pounds per square meter for cooling purposes, whereas the solar house requires a mere 1.33. The overall energy requirements for the contemporary house, according the Energy 10 calculations, reaches a high of 368 kWh/m² as compared to 121 kWh/m² of the Experimental Solar House.

Figure 7.27 Comparative Barographs Energy Total annual energy use, plus breakout by heating, cooling, fan, and "other" uses (everything else)

Figure 7.28 Monthly Average Daily Energy Use Graphs

6. CONCLUSION

Thus the construction of the solar house has a purpose that is multifaceted. It is an environmental success as well as an architectural one. The house itself will be able to provide excellent indoor air quality and natural lighting.

When a Cypriot contemporary house was compared to a traditional house, the energy performance of the original insulated traditional house is superior to the contemporary house, with no energy-efficient considerations. Therefore, since the Experimental Solar House was designed and constructed using researched material of traditional houses, once compared with a contemporary house the results were easy to assume. The Experimental Solar House proved to be far superior in its energy-saving performance.

The following techniques were used in historical and traditional houses, can be used through passive design today and are used for the design of the Experimental Solar House:

- Clear topographical clarifications
- The positions in orientation to the sun path either to avoid direct sunlight entering the building of the opposite.
- The exploitation of breezes for ventilation and cross ventilation in the room
- The awareness and exploitation of the nature of flora and its use for practical functions (e.g. medicinal plants, fruit-bearing trees)
- A good insulation of walls (40-50cm width) and roofs,
- The small openings on the external walls for maximum insulation.

These elements can be found in constructions created since 7000B.C. Elements, which are now fundamentally used in passive architecture.

Early examples include:

- The Solarium was predominant whether acting as an arched corridor, as a central axis or even when it evolved into a self-contained space.
- Courtyards, planted mostly with deciduous vegetation like grapevines, providing shade in the summer and admitting the sun in the winter
- Almost all openings placed on the south wall providing natural light and heat.
- Arseres allowed lighter hot air to go out of the house and be replaced by cooler air from outside in the summer
- Thymes (small dense bushes) blocked the arseres in the winter and provided thermal insulation.
- Roofs and floors were constructed in a typical insulating manner
- Courtyards were built to facing southwards, acting as a sunspace, receiving desired solar radiation in winter.
- The solarium admitted the rays from the winter sun to penetrate and so solar radiation could be utilised in winter.

- In multiple thermal modes and varied design, the courtyard and the solarium moderate high summer temperatures- their careful construction combined with the surrounding landscaping lower the temperatures around the building.

These examples, illustrate strong characteristics of historical architecture, which serve as fine examples of energy-saving architecture today and are used on the Experimental Solar House.

The following conclusions were made concerning thermal comfort in Cyprus:

- Thermal comfort zones depend on regional climate.
- An average of 19.5°C – 29°C is the proposed temperature, within the comfort zone limits of Cyprus
- An average of 20-75% is the proposed relative humidity, within the comfort zone limits of Cyprus.
- The best thermal comfort is achieved in the months of April, May, October and November. These months needed no extra heating or cooling. The results showed that to achieve thermal comfort conditions, ventilation is required in the summer months (June, July, August and September). In this case, natural ventilation actually occurs, or if there are no breezes, then ceiling fans are applied. In the months of December, January, February and March passive solar gains are used to achieve thermal comfort. It must be noted that steps should be taken to avoid over heating in the summer. The same is to be said for the passive cooling needs in the summer. The results show that all heating requirements are covered through solar energy, while natural ventilation or ceiling fans cover all the cooling needs.

The development of passive solar systems is significant to the economic, social and political issues. The best-known applications of passive solar systems were researched taking into consideration the advantages and disadvantages for Lefkosia were being researched and it is concluded that the passive systems that are most suited for Cyprus and used on the Experimental Solar House, are:

- Direct Gain: the simplest solar heating system and can be easiest to build. Areas of glazing not only admit solar radiation for heating but also high levels of daylighting and good visual conditions for the outside. Glazing is well researched and cheap and a material readily available. With adequate insulation of the

building, it is possible to rely totally on direct gain as a passive solar system used in the case of Cyprus.

- Shape of building: rectangular but compact design (aspect ratio 1:1.33) with the longer axis pointing East and West.
- Thermal Insulation: position of insulation externally on walls and roof. Thickness 70mm expanded polystyrene. Overall U-value of walls and roof 0.6 W/m²K.
- Thermal Storage (Interior Mass): The simplest heat storage approach is to construct the building of massive structural materials (reinforced concrete or brick blocks) insulated on the exterior, to couple the mass of the indoor space
- Glazing: For direct gain systems, south facing window area greater than about 10-12% of floor area require thermal mass, well distributed over floors, walls and ceilings to reduce temperature swings. 5% north wall openings are sufficient for cross ventilation during summer nights. Types to be used: Low emmissivity glazing, argon-filled, double-glazed. Shading can be easily controlled for the non-heating season.
- Solar Control: By use of orientation (one of the long walls is facing south so that the available solar radiation is exploited in the winter), external shading devices, vegetation (shade deciduous trees are excellent for shade in summer while allowing sun through the winter).
- Natural Ventilation: By use of cross ventilation, stack effect, night ventilation and ceiling fans.

Upon construction of the Experimental Solar House, careful monitoring was pursued, in order to measure its performance in use. Through monitoring the house from the 27/11/1999 until 18/12/2001, using computer data loggers, the following can be concluded: The internal temperature and relative humidity throughout the year remained steady (within the thermal comfort limits), despite the instability of external temperatures and humidity percentages.

Comparative annual energy use was performed using computer simulation software Energy 10 resulting that the most energy efficient is the solar house (121 kWh/m²) following the traditional (243 kWh/m²) and final the contemporary (368 kWh/m²).

Because of Lefkosia's climate, passive solar architecture works to its full capacity. This means that, a passive solar house has 100% energy saving potential. This theory has not remained at its

conceptual stage as the Experimental Solar House has demonstrated it in practice.

ⁱ For further bibliography on the popular houses of Cyprus see, Papacharalampous G., *Η κυπριακή λαϊκή οίκια*, 1968 and St. Sinos's *Αναδρομή στη λαϊκή αρχιτεκτονική της Κύπρου*, 1976. Also see Hatzimichali, V., *Κυπριακή λαϊκή αρχιτεκτονική*, Report of the Department of Antiquities, Cyprus 1967. 87ff and St. Sinos, *The folk Architecture and Art of Cyprus*, Report of the Department of Antiquities, Cyprus, 1984, 354ff.

ⁱⁱ *Fernandes, E., and Yannas, S., 1988, Energy and Buildings for Temperate Climates - A Mediterranean Regional Approach, Proceedings of the PLEA 88 Conference, Porto, Pergamon Press, Oxford.*

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^{iv} Lapithis, P. *Solar Architecture in Cyprus*. PhD theses, University of Wales, UK, 2002

^v Ibid

^{vi} Ibid